

Thermodynamic Study of Uranium Extraction from Tunisian Wet Process Phosphoric Acid

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Abstract : In the present paper, an experimental investigation was conducted to study the thermodynamic of uranium extraction from Tunisian wet phosphoric acid using the synergistic solvent mixture of di-2-ethylhexyl phosphoric acid (DEHPA) and trioctyl phosphine oxid (TOPO) diluted in kerosene. The effect of different factors affecting the extraction process (temperature, TOPO and DEHPA concentrations) has been investigated. The obtained data of temperature effect on the extraction showed that the enthalpy change is $-35,8 \text{ kJ.mol}^{-1}$. The slope analysis method was used for determining the stoichiometry of the extracted species.

Keywords : DEHPA-TOPO, extraction, phosphoric acid, stoichiometry, uranium.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014